

Impact of Antenna Position and Radiation Patterns on Target Detection in a Highway Environment Utilizing ICAS Extended Model

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Abstract—In this paper, we explore the impact of different antenna positions and radiation patterns on the channel performance of an Integrated Communication and Sensing (ICAS) extended model in a highway environment. We have considered a 3-dB omnidirectional Transmitter (Tx) and a directive Receiver (Rx) for our analysis. The antenna radiation patterns of patch and horn antennas are used for the directive receiver. In our system, we have considered three different setups. In the first setup, Rx has a directive antenna (either horn or patch) installed on the front bumper of the car. In the second setup, the directive antenna is installed on the back bumper of the car. For the third setup, the radiation patterns for the front and back bumper of the car are combined, thus giving rise to Combined Gain Pattern (CGP). The channel responses for the front and back bumper-placed antenna setups are evaluated and compared with the respective CGP setup channel response. The performance of an ICAS system depends on the successful detection of targets. We have considered two types of scatterers in our system. The moving vehicles on the road represent Dynamic Targets (DT) whereas, stationary point reflection sources along the sides of the highway represent Diffuse (DI) scattering components. We have shown in our results that the CGP setup outperforms the front and back bumper-located antenna setups in terms of channel magnitude and accurate target detection capabilities. Moreover, CGP setup helps in modeling the environment better as compared to front and back-bumper installed setups.

Index Terms—Selection combining, target detection, ICAS, antenna placement, antenna radiation pattern.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the field of Integrated Communication and Sensing (ICAS) has gained attention of the researchers due to its numerous advantages over traditional modes of communication and sensing. In ICAS the functionalities of radar and communication are unified under a single platform. This stems from the fact that both technologies have many underlying similarities such as signal processing, propagation medium and mechanisms, frequency band, and hardware. Efficient spectrum utilization and hardware costs are a few of the many reasons to explore ICAS [1], [2]. ICAS is anticipated to play a crucial role in many industrial applications including vehicular networks, indoor localization, Autonomous Driving (AD), and drone networks [3].

The ICAS enabled Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) setup represents a critical application scenario that is essential for the future Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS). Different

channel models for the traditional V2V communications have been proposed over the years. These include standardized models such as COST action projects, 3GPP Spatial Channel Model (SCM) [4], WINNER channel models [5], IEEE 802.11n [6] & IEEE 802.16ac [7], [8]. However, as of now, ICAS enabled V2V setup lacks a mature channel model that could facilitate both sensing and communication.

The vehicles designed in the automobile industry are expected to contain multiple antennas distributed on the surface which enables the use of Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) and antenna diversity techniques. This results in enhancing data rates and reliability in V2V networks. However, it also makes channel modeling an arduous job. Several studies provide measurements for modeling vehicular channels with different antenna setups and diversity techniques [9], [10]. Therefore, for the accurate modeling of V2V channels, it is critically important to take into consideration the impact of antenna placement and geometry of cars. Numerous studies have explored these impacts for V2V communications. However, there remains a notable gap in research concerning antenna placement and radiation patterns specifically tailored for ICAS enabled V2V setup.

In our study, we explore the impact of antenna position and radiation patterns on target detection capability and channel magnitude. In this paper, we have adopted the extended ICAS propagation model inspired by [11], [12]. The channel model presented in [11] represents a traditional V2V communication system. It does not consider target detection or sensing capability. The model was extended and ICAS capability was integrated [12]. However, the extended ICAS model only considers omnidirectional Transmitter (Tx) and Receiver (Rx) and lacks the directivity factor. In this paper, we integrate a directive Rx with different antenna radiation patterns and placement into the model and explore the impact of antenna placement on the channel performance and target detection capability. We considered three links: 1) Direct Link (DL) (Tx → Rx), 2) Indirect Link (IDL) from Dynamic Targets (DT) (Tx → DT → Rx), and 3) IDL from Diffuse (DI) scatterers (Tx → DI → Rx) to explore the impact of directive Rx and radiation patterns on these links.

Fig. 1: Geometry of the highway and different setups

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: Sec. II describes the highway topology, vehicle routes, and utilized simulation tools. Next, Sec. III describes antenna placement setups and integration into the model. Sec. IV depicts the extended ICAS channel model used for the simulations. Sec. V shows the simulation results whereas the paper is concluded and future works are given in Sec. VI.

II. HIGHWAY TOPOLOGY, VEHICLES ROUTES, AND SIMULATION TOOLS

In this section, we describe the highway topology along with the distribution of DT and DI scatterers. Moreover, this section will also provide information about vehicular traffic setup and simulation tools used for traffic generation and signal processing.

A. Highway Topology

In this paper, we considered a similar environment as in [12]. A 6-lane (3-lanes per direction) highway with a length $l_{road}=1000$ m and a width $w_{road}=27$ m. The width of each lane is $w_{lane}=4.5$ m. We use a fixed number of four DT that contribute towards the channel response. These DT represent moving vehicles and are placed in different lanes with different initial positions and velocities. Fig. 1 shows the lane numbers and their respective positions along with the direction of motion of the vehicles¹. On both sides of the road, the DI components representing vegetation, scatterers, and points of reflection beyond the road, are considered to model their impact on the overall channel performance and target detection. To model the DI region, a similar approach used in [11] is adopted. The density of the DI scatterers within a given length of one meter is given by χ_{diff} . The width of the DI region is $w_{diff}=5$ m. The distance from the center of the road to the first DI component is $w_{first}=15.5$ m. The x-coordinates of the DI scatterers are modeled by a uniform distribution i.e., $x_{diff} \sim \mathcal{U}[x_{min}, x_{max}]$. Their y-coordinates are also drawn from the uniform distribution i.e., $y_{diff} \sim \mathcal{U}[y_{1,diff} - w_{diff}/2, y_{1,diff} + w_{diff}/2]$ or $y_{diff} \sim \mathcal{U}[y_{2,diff} - w_{diff}/2, y_{2,diff} + w_{diff}/2]$, where $[y_{1,diff}]$ and $[y_{2,diff}]$ represent the center of the DI region on both sides

¹In Fig.1, only one link is shown to represent IDL from DT and DI scatterers. However, for simulations, the links from all DT and DI components are considered.

of the highway. Further, we consider a boundary region of $d_{gap}=2$ m between the start of the DI and the outermost lanes. In our simulations, $[y_{1,diff}] = -17.5$ m and $[y_{2,diff}] = 17.5$ m.

B. Vehicles and Routes

The traffic is modeled in such a way that the Tx and Rx are located in the middle lanes (L-1, RL-1) as shown in Fig. 1, moving towards each other (v_{dir}). There are two DT (V-0, V-2) in lanes (L-0, L-2) and moving in the same direction as Tx. Whereas the remaining two DT (RV-0, RV-2) are located in lanes (RL-0, RL-2) and moving in the same direction as Rx. The DT reach the center and cross one another at different time instants depending upon their initial position and velocity. Vehicles are assigned variable velocities and starting positions to represent a realistic scenario.

C. Simulation Tools

For our simulation, we use three mathematical tools.

- For the generation of traffic on the road, we use Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) [13], which is an open-source tool used for simulating and analyzing traffic.
- Radiation pattern simulations for the horn and patch antennas were executed using Altair FEKO's Multi-Level Fast Multipole Method (MLFMM) solver at 5.9 GHz frequency.
- MATLAB is used for the signal processing part. Different channel parameters and responses for DL and IDL are calculated. Moreover, received power, excess delay, Doppler shift, trajectory information, and detection capabilities are also evaluated with MATLAB

III. ANTENNA INTEGRATION SCENARIO

This study aims to perform a comparative analysis between highly directive and low directive antennas for sensing applications. Hence, two distinct types of antennas, namely the horn antenna (high directivity) and the patch antenna (low directivity), have been chosen for consideration. To ensure accuracy, these antennas were integrated into a car model. Specifically, we utilized a simplified hatchback car model to replicate the installed antenna pattern. A visual representation of the car model and the placement of the antennas is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Car model along with antenna locations

As discussed in [14], in terms of antenna integration KPIs for V2X communication, antennas positioned at the front and back of the vehicle are more advantageous than those on the sides. Therefore, considering the potential for utilizing V2X communication antennas for sensing purposes, our study focuses on analyzing the antenna locations at the front and back of the vehicle. Furthermore, the impact of the front and back antenna's Combined Gain Pattern (CGP) on the overall sensing performance has also been assessed. The CGP of the two radiation patterns was achieved utilizing the equation [15]:

$$G_{combined} = \max(G_{front-antenna}, G_{back-antenna}) \quad (1)$$

The individual radiation patterns of the front and back antenna and the CGP for both patch and horn antennas are shown in Fig. 3 and 4. Since mostly, the V2V communication takes place near the horizon, therefore the radiation pattern at $\theta=90^\circ$ (based on the coordinate system of Fig. 2) has been considered in this work.

Fig. 3: Patch antenna radiation patterns

IV. ICAS EXTENDED CHANNEL MODEL

The ICAS model in [12] does not consider directivity. In this study, we have integrated the directivity to explore the impact of different radiation patterns on channel magnitude and target detection. Simplified Ray Tracing (RT) is used to generate channel responses for all the links. The Channel Impulse Response (CIR) can be represented as:

$$h(t) = \sum_s G_{Tx}(\theta = 0, \phi_s) G_{Rx}(\theta = 0, \phi_s) \gamma_s e^{j2\pi\alpha_s t} \delta(t - \tau_s), \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4: Horn antenna radiation patterns

where τ_s and α_s represent the excess delay and Doppler shift of the respective path s . For Tx, a constant 3 dB G_{Tx} is considered whereas the G_{Rx} of the Rx varies in the azimuth plane given by ϕ_s . The amplitude of the path s is represented by γ_s . We have considered three major contributors² to the overall channel response in our simulations.

A. DL Component

The DL component defines the link between Tx and Rx when no vehicles or obstacles are blocking the path. The DL channel response is given by:

$$h_{DL}(t) = g_{Tx} g_{Rx} \gamma_{DL} e^{j2\pi\alpha_{DL} t} \delta(t - \tau_{DL}), \quad (3)$$

where α_{DL} and τ_{DL} represent the Doppler shift and delay for the DL component. The amplitude γ_{DL} is given by [11]:

$$\gamma_{DL} = P_{ref,DL}^{1/2} \left(\frac{d_{ref}}{d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}} \right)^{n_{DL}/2}, \quad (4)$$

where $P_{ref,DL}$ and n_{DL} represent the reference power and path-loss exponent for the DL. The DL distance between Tx and Rx is represented by $d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}$. The delay and Doppler shift mathematical expressions for the DL component are given in (4) and (5) of [12].

B. DT Component

DT components refer to the IDL, which result from other moving vehicles on the highway, i.e. Tx \rightarrow k \rightarrow Rx (where k denotes the k^{th} DT). The DT channel response can be mathematically expressed as:

$$h_{DT}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K g_{(Tx,k)} g_{(Rx,k)} \gamma_k e^{j2\pi\alpha_k t} \delta(t - \tau_k), \quad (5)$$

where α_k and τ_k represent the Doppler shift and delay for the k^{th} DT. K is the total number of DT components in our scenario. The amplitude γ_k is given by:

$$\gamma_k = P_{ref,k}^{1/2} \left(\frac{d_{ref}}{d_{Tx \rightarrow k}} \right)^{n_k/2} \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{RCS,k}}{4\pi(d_{k \rightarrow Rx})^{n_k}}}, \quad (6)$$

²In our simulations, we have not considered the contributions from Static Target (ST) (road signs, signboards, etc.).

Fig. 5: Channel magnitude for horn antenna

where $P_{ref,k}$ is the reference power for the k^{th} DT and n_k is the path-loss exponent. $d_{Tx \rightarrow k}$ and $d_{k \rightarrow Rx}$ represent the distance from Tx to k^{th} DT and k^{th} DT to Rx, respectively. $\sigma_{RCS,k}$ denotes the Radar Cross Section (RCS) of the k^{th} DT. The delay and Doppler shift mathematical expressions for the DT are given in (8) and (9) of [12].

C. DI Component

The DI components represent the point scatterers or vegetation located along the sides of the highway. The DI channel response can be mathematically expressed as:

$$h_{DI}(t) = \sum_{q=1}^Q g_{(Tx,q)} g_{(Rx,q)} \gamma_q e^{j2\pi\alpha_q t} \delta(t - \tau_q), \quad (7)$$

where α_q and τ_q represent the Doppler shift and delay for the q^{th} DI component. Q is the total number of DI scatterers in our scenario. The amplitude of DI scatterer is modeled according to the classical Geometry-based Stochastic Channel Model (GBSCM) approach and is represented as [11]:

$$\gamma_q = P_{ref,q}^{1/2} c_q \left(\frac{d_{ref}}{d_{Tx \rightarrow q} \times d_{q \rightarrow Rx}} \right)^{n_q/2}, \quad (8)$$

where $P_{ref,q}$ and n_q represent reference power and path-loss exponent for the q^{th} DI component. $d_{Tx \rightarrow q}$ and $d_{q \rightarrow Rx}$ represent the distance from Tx to the q^{th} DI scatterer and from the q^{th} DI scatterer to Rx, respectively. c_q denotes zero-mean complex Gaussian variable. The delay and Doppler shift for DI scatterers can be calculated similarly to the DT components given in (8) and (9) of [12].

D. Overall Channel Response

The overall channel response is derived by adding the contributions from the individual channel responses (i.e., DL component, DT components, and DI components), and is given as:

$$h(t) = h_{DL}(t) + h_{DT}(t) + h_{DI}(t). \quad (9)$$

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we present the simulation results for the aforementioned scenarios at a carrier frequency of $f_c = 5.9$

GHz. We have considered a constant Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP) value for all the setups to have a fair comparison. The channel magnitude for the DL from Tx and IDL from DT and DI components are calculated and summed at the Rx. The rest of the considered parameters along with vehicles' velocity in different lanes are given in Table I.

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
Bandwidth (B)	50 MHz
EIRP	23 dBm
Vehicles' speed in different lanes (L-0,L-1,L-2,RL-0,RL-1,RL-2)	(32,30,27,27,30,32) m/s
Simulation Time (t_{sim})	15.99 s
Sample Time	0.01 s
Radar Cross Section (σ_{RCS})	10 dBsm
Horn Reference Power ($P_{ref,i}$) where $i \in (DL, k, q)$	(-33, -38, 76) dB
Patch Reference Power ($P_{ref,i}$) where $i \in (DL, k, q)$	(-42, -47, 68) dB
PL Exponents (n_i where $i \in (DL, k, q)$)	(1.8, 2.0, 5.4)
DI Scatterers Density χ_{diff}	1 m ⁻²

A. Horn Antenna Setup

The channel response for CGP, front and back bumper installed horn antenna is given in Fig. 5. For the front bumper installed setup, the DL results in the highest channel magnitude for the first half of the simulation as shown in Fig. 5a. At around 8 s, Tx and Rx cross each other. After 8 s, the radiation pattern of the Rx points in the opposite direction. As a result, the DL channel magnitude drops below IDL channel magnitude. The channel magnitude of joint DT is always higher as compared to DI scatterers' channel magnitude. The DT in different lanes cross one another at different instants e.g., between $6s \leq t_{sim} \leq 10s$. During this interval, the distance among DT, Tx, and Rx is minimum and as a result, the respective channel magnitude of joint DT and DI scatterers becomes higher in the said duration. However, the DL channel magnitude remains higher than the DI channel magnitude in the interval $10s \leq t_{sim} \leq 16s$.

The channel response for the back bumper installed setup is given in Fig. 5b. For the first half of the simulation i.e., up

Fig. 6: Channel magnitude for patch antenna

to 7.5 s, the channel magnitude of DT remains the highest. This stems from the fact that the main lobe of the Rx is pointing in the opposite direction. During a short interval ($6 \text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 8 \text{ s}$), the channel magnitude of DI components becomes higher than the DL. The channel magnitude for joint DT remains always higher than the DI scatterers' channel magnitude, except in the duration $7 \text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 9 \text{ s}$. This results from lower gain values for DT in that duration.

The CGP horn antenna setup results in a better performance as compared to the front and back bumper-installed horn antenna setups. The DL always results in a better performance as compared to IDL except in the duration when Tx and Rx are parallel to each other i.e., around 8 s. The channel magnitude of DT remains equal to or higher than the DI scatterers' channel magnitude as shown in Fig. 5c. It can be seen from Fig. 5 that the CGP setup outperforms the front and back bumper setups resulting in the highest channel magnitude.

B. Patch Antenna Setup

The channel magnitude for different setups using patch antennas is shown in Fig. 6. The channel response is similar to the horn antenna setup channel response. The channel magnitude for the front bumper installed setup is given in Fig. 6a. The DL dominates over the IDL for the first half of the simulation. After Tx and Rx cross each other at 8 s, the main lobe of the patch antenna points in the opposite direction. As a result, the channel magnitude of the DL becomes lower than the IDL channel magnitude. Among the IDL, the channel magnitude of the DT always remains higher than the DI components.

The channel magnitude for the back bumper installed setup is represented by Fig. 6b. During the first half, the main lobe of the patch antenna is directed away from the Tx. Hence, the DL channel magnitude is lower than IDL for the first half of the simulation. However, the main lobe is aligned with the Tx after the cross-over, which results in a higher channel magnitude for the DL. The joint DT channel magnitude also shows a similar pattern. For the first half, the channel magnitude is higher than the DI components' channel magnitude. However, after 7 s, the channel magnitude of the DT becomes lower than DI

components. This stems from the fact that the gain associated with the DT is comparatively lower in the later half depending upon their respective Angle of Arrival (AoA) and associated gain values. The CGP patch antenna setup results in a much better performance as compared to the front and back bumper-installed setups as shown in Fig. 6c. The channel magnitude of the DL remains highest throughout the simulation, except for the duration in which both Tx and Rx are parallel to one another. Similarly, the channel magnitude of the DT remains higher than the DI components throughout the simulation. This results in better target detection and hence improves the overall performance.

C. Overall Channel Magnitude

The overall channel magnitude comparison for different setups is shown in Fig. 7. The CGP setup for horn and patch antennas outperforms their respective front and back bumper-installed setups. CGP horn antenna setup results in a higher channel magnitude throughout the simulation. In the interval $6 \text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 10 \text{ s}$, the CGP horn setup results in a gain of 18 dB as compared to its counterparts. Similarly, it can be seen that the CGP patch antenna setup also outperforms front and back bumper-installed patch antenna setups. The CGP patch

Fig. 7: Overall channel magnitude comparison

Fig. 8: Target detection for horn antenna setup at $t_{\text{sim}} = 6$ s

Fig. 9: Target detection for horn antenna setup at $t_{\text{sim}} = 10$ s

setup results in a gain of 8 dB as compared to the front and back bumper installed setups. In the CGP setups, the channel magnitude of DT remains higher as compared to DI components. This ensures better communication and target detection capability than front and back-bumper-installed setups. The horn antenna configuration demonstrates superior performance for a constant EIRP in comparison to the patch antenna. This advantage is attributed to the horn antenna's higher gain.

D. Target Detection with Horn Antenna Setup

The signal processing for target detection is done by using classical radar sensing techniques. In our scenario, it is assumed that the Rx has the perfect knowledge of the Tx signal. Inspired by [16], the main radar signal processing steps include element-wise division to obtain the channel response, 2D-(I)FFT to get the distance-velocity parameters, windowing for sidelobes reduction, etc. The distance-velocity plots for the horn antenna setup at different time instants are shown in Fig. 8 and 9. At $t_{\text{sim}} = 6$ s, the main lobe of the Rx is pointing towards the Tx for the front bumper setup. Whereas in the back bumper setup, the main lobe is pointing in the opposite direction. In Fig. 8a, the DL from Tx is very prominent (-

50 dB). The difference in the received power (P_{rcv}) of DT and DI with the highest power is comparatively low i.e., around 35 dB. The DT can still be distinguished from the DI. However, not all the DT can be distinguished successfully. The red and black ellipses indicate the presence of the Tx from the DL, and the DT from the IDL, respectively. The rest indicates the DI components, which are treated as clutter.

Similarly, the distance-velocity plot for the back bumper setup is given in Fig. 8b. Since now the back bumper antenna installed at Rx points in the opposite direction of Tx, the DL from Tx has a lower P_{rcv} as compared to IDL from DT. The P_{rcv} of the DT is also higher than that of the DI. However, the difference between the DT and the DI with the highest P_{rcv} is significantly reduced. Hence, it becomes difficult to differentiate between DT and the clutter. The distance-velocity plot for the CGP horn antenna setup at 6 s is given in Fig. 8c. It can be seen that the DL from Tx has the highest P_{rcv} followed by DT and DI. With a difference of about 20 dB, the DT can be distinguished from the clutter.

At $t_{\text{sim}} = 10$ s, the Tx and the Rx are now moving in opposite directions. As a result, the distance-velocity plots of the front

Fig. 10: Target detection for patch antenna setup at $t_{\text{sim}} = 6$ s

Fig. 11: Target detection for patch antenna setup at $t_{\text{sim}} = 10$ s

and back bumper setups are seen interchanged as compared to the setup at $t_{\text{sim}} = 6$ s. The distance-velocity plot for the front bumper setup is shown in Fig. 9a. The P_{rcv} of the DL is lower than that of the IDL. The DT have a higher P_{rcv} and can be distinguished from the clutter. However, the P_{rcv} of some of the DI scatterers is very close to the DTs' P_{rcv} . Thus, rendering the detection more complicated. On the other hand, the DL for the back bumper setup results in the highest P_{rcv} as shown in Fig. 9b. The P_{rcv} of the IDL is significantly lower than the DL. The DT can be hardly distinguished from the clutter. The DL in the CGP setup results in the highest P_{rcv} followed by DT and DI as shown in Fig. 9c. Although some of the DT can be differentiated from the clutter, there are DI scatterers with P_{rcv} very close to the DT.

The CGP setup outperforms the front and back bumper setups. In the CGP setup, the DL from Tx can be clearly distinguished throughout the simulation. Moreover, the P_{rcv} of the DT is also higher, resulting in the successful detection of targets from the clutter. The front and back bumper-installed setups, depending on the direction of the main radiation lobe, can only successfully detect the DL and IDL from DT for

half of the simulation duration. Moreover, the CGP setup results in more accurate modeling of the environment as compared to its counterparts, which is very important for reliable communication and error-less detection.

E. Target Detection with Patch Antenna Setup

The distance-velocity plots for the patch antenna setup at different time instants are shown in Fig. 10 and 11. The main radiation lobe of the front bumper setup points towards Tx and the back bumper setup points in the opposite direction to the Tx at $t_{\text{sim}} = 6$ s. It can be seen from Fig. 10a, the DL from Tx is prominent (-75 dB). The difference in the P_{rcv} of DT and DI with the highest power is comparatively low. The DT can hardly be distinguished from the clutter. Similarly, the distance-velocity plot for the back antenna setup is given in Fig. 10b. Before the cross-over takes place, the DL from Tx has a very low P_{rcv} (-115 dB) as the main radiation lobe points in the opposite direction. The Tx from DL can be detected. However, the P_{rcv} of DL is much lower than the IDL. The P_{rcv} for the DT is higher than the DI. However, the difference between the DT and the DI with the highest P_{rcv} is significantly reduced. Hence, it becomes difficult to differentiate between

DT and the clutter. The distance-velocity plot for the CGP patch antenna at 6 s is given in Fig. 10c. It can be seen that the DL from Tx has the highest P_{rcv} followed by DT and DI. However, the difference between P_{rcv} of DT and DI with the highest P_{rcv} is not significantly high as shown in Fig. 10c. The P_{rcv} values for the clutter in patch antenna setups are lower than the horn antenna setups. Most of the clutter detected has P_{rcv} lower than -150 dB. For the horn antenna setup, clutter has P_{rcv} in the range from -120 dB till -200 dB. This is because of the lower gain of the patch antenna.

Similarly, the distance-velocity plot for the front bumper setup at $t_{sim} = 10$ s is shown in Fig. 11a. The P_{rcv} from the DL is very low. But it can be still detected. The DT have a higher P_{rcv} and can be distinguished from the clutter. However, the P_{rcv} of some of the DI is very close to the DTs' P_{rcv} . Thus, making the detection more difficult. The DL for the back bumper installed antenna setup results in the highest P_{rcv} as shown in Fig. 11b. The P_{rcv} of the IDL is significantly lower than the DL as clear from the Fig. 6b. The DT can be hardly distinguished from the clutter. The DL in the CGP setup results in the highest P_{rcv} followed by DT and DI as shown in Fig. 11c. The CGP setup can successfully detect the DT throughout the simulation. Moreover, the CGP setup detects the environment in a better way as compared to the front and back bumper-installed setups. The P_{rcv} from the clutter is lower than the DT which results in a higher target detection accuracy.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have integrated different antenna radiation patterns into the extended Integrated Communication and Sensing (ICAS) channel model. We have simulated and compared results by placing antennae in different setups (front and back bumper) of the Receiver (Rx) with a constant gain omnidirectional Transmitter (Tx). We have shown in our results that a Combined Gain Pattern (CGP) antenna setup outperforms front and back bumper-installed setups in terms of channel magnitude and target detection capabilities. CGP Horn and Patch antenna setup successfully detects Dynamic Targets (DT) throughout the simulation. It is of imperative importance to model the environment as accurately as possible for the design of proper signal-processing algorithms. A CGP setup facilitates accomplishing this objective. Thus, proving that CGP setup is a better option to utilize as compared to the other setups. For a constant Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP) value, the horn antenna setup produces better results as compared to the patch antenna setup. In the future, this work can be extended by utilizing different diversity and Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) schemes to explore its impact on channel magnitude and detection. Moreover, different antenna placement combinations such as front or back bumper with side mirrors can be explored as well.

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